

Computation of Analog Theorems for the Annamalai Iota Function

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Abstract: The Annamalai iota function is the most important special function in the area of analytic number theory. This paper presents analog theorems for the Annamalai iota function using the geometric series.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the summation of series involving the Annamalai iota function [17,18]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [19].

2. A Theorem on the Alternative Harmonic Series

The alternative harmonic series is defined by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{8} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}.$$

Theorem 2.1: The sum of alternative harmonic series is equal to $\ln 2$.

$$i.e. \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Proof. This theorem is proved using the infinite geometric series as follows:

$$\text{Let } S = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

$$\Rightarrow xS = x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + \dots$$

$$\text{Then, } (S - xS) = 1 \Rightarrow (1 - x)S = 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - x} = S.$$

$$i.e. \frac{1}{1 - x} = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

Integrating on both sides with respect to x :

$$\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx.$$

First, let us find the solution of $\int \frac{1}{1-x} dx$.

Let $u = 1 - x$; $du = -dx$; $dx = -du$.

Then, $\int \frac{1}{1-x} dx = - \int \frac{1}{u} du = - \ln u = - \ln(1-x)$.

Now, $\int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx = - \ln(1-x)$.

$$\Rightarrow x + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^6}{6} + \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^8}{8} + \dots = - \ln(1-x).$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} \dots = - \ln(1-x) \Rightarrow - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} = \ln(1-x).$$

Substituting $x = -1$ on both sides:

$$- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \ln(1 - (-1)) \Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

3. Analog Theorems for Annamalai Iota Function

The Annamalai iota function $l(s)$ for all complex numbers is defined by

$$l(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s}.$$

The Annamalai iota function $l(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $Re(s) > 0$.

Theorem 3.1: $\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \ln 2$.

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the geometric series:

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{2^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} - \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} - \dots \right)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} - \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{6^s} - \dots$$

By simplifying this equation using the sum of geometric series, we get

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^s} - 1 \right) - \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{3^s} - 1 \right) + \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^s} - 1 \right) - \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{5^s} - 1 \right) + \dots$$

$$\text{Here, } \left(\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^s} - 1 \right) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{k}} - 1 = \frac{k}{k-1} - 1 = \frac{k-k+1}{k-1} = \frac{1}{k-1} \text{ for } k = 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$$

Now, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Theorem 3.2: $\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = 2 \ln 2 - 1.$

Proof. Case (i): Let us prove this theorem using the theorem 3.1.

$$\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = l(1) + 1 + l(2) + 1 + l(3) + 1 + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}$$

$$l(2) + 1 + l(3) + 1 + l(4) + 1 + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} - (l(1) + 1)$$

$$\text{where } l(1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = - \ln 2.$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} - (l(1) + 1) = \ln 2 - (- \ln 2 + 1)$$

By simplifying this equation, we get

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = 2 \ln 2 - 1.$$

Hence proved.

Case(ii): Let us prove this theorem using the property $\sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \sum_{q=0}^{\infty} f(x, y) = \sum_{q=0}^{\infty} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} f(x, y).$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left(\sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left(\left\{ \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right\} - \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right)$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left(\left\{ \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right\} - \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (-1)^n \left(\left\{ \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{n}} \right\} - \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right)$$

$$\text{Here, } (-1)^n \left(\left\{ \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{n}} \right\} - \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right) = (-1)^n \left(\frac{1}{(n-1)n} \right) = \frac{(-1)^n}{(n-1)} - \frac{(-1)^n}{n}$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(-1)^n}{(n-1)} - \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{(n-1)} - \left(- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} + 1 \right)$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (l(s) + 1) = \ln 2 - (- \ln 2 + 1) = 2 \ln 2 - 1.$$

Hence proved.

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author has proved few analog theorems for the Annamalai iota zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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